

Mapping the County Energy Planning Ecosystem in Kenya

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Executive Summary

This working paper maps the ecosystem of actors involved in county-level energy planning in Kenya. Drawing from an online workshop and expert stakeholder interviews alongside a review of relevant law and policy, it maps the status of energy planning across counties, the actors involved, and planning approaches used. The aim is to generate a concise summary of ongoing work in this space as a quick start guide to anyone seeking to engage within it.

We identify six counties which have a complete county energy plan (i.e., Kitui, Marsabit, Nairobi, Nakuru, Narok, Turkana), and fifteen counties which have ongoing efforts to produce these plans. Key funders of county energy plan development are the United Kingdom, Germany, and the European Union. The European Union is the largest player with its sizeable Sustainable Energy Technical Assistance (SETA) programme. Numerous organisations provide technical support for county-level energy planning. These include development organisations (i.e., Innovation Energie Développement, Practical Action, the International Institute for Environment and Development, the Kenya Climate Change Working Group, the Sustainable Energy Access Forum Kenya, the World Resources Institute); academic institutions (i.e., Loughborough University, the African Centre for Technology Studies, Strathmore University, the Kenya Forestry Research Institute); and private sector actors or consultancies (i.e., Ricardo, EED Advisory).

Through stakeholder interviews, we identify key allies and collaborators to county energy planning at local and national levels. Stakeholders report that working with a local civil society organisation (e.g., Caritas Kitui, Narok County Natural Resource Network) is the most effective way to engage for data collection and baselining. To garner support and buy-in for the planning process, they note that it is critical to engage the County Executive Committee, particularly the member responsible for energy, as well as the County Assembly, Governor, and Director for Economic Planning. Nationally, key partners for coordination and data flow are Kenya Power, the National Bureau of Statistics, the Ministry of Energy, and the Rural Electrification and Renewable Energy Corporation.

While all county-level energy planning in Kenya is to be guided by the Integrated National Energy Planning framework, efforts to date use different methodologies. The most commonly used approach so far is the Energy Delivery Model method, which has been adopted in some form across all counties supported in the Sustainable Energy Technical Assistance programme. This method, while thorough, is quite resource intensive. County energy plans produced by independent actors often use methods of their own design, which, while bearing similarity to the Energy Delivery Model, omit or change various elements. Lacking defined method names, these are referred to herein based on the implementing organisation's name.

The results of this ecosystem mapping are summarized in the table below.

County	CEP Status	Year	Funder	Programme	Organizations (lead in bold , local partner in <i>italics</i>)	Approach
Baringo	Ongoing		UK	PACT	Ricardo , KCCWG	Ricardo/KCCWG approach
Bomet	Ongoing		EU	SETA	SETA consortium , KCCWG, SEAF-K	EDM
Garissa	Ongoing		EU	SETA	SETA consortium	EDM
Kakamega	Ongoing		EU	SETA	SETA consortium	EDM
Kiambu	Ongoing		EU	SETA	SETA consortium	EDM
Kilifi	Ongoing		EU	SETA	SETA consortium	EDM
Kisii	Ongoing		EU	SETA	SETA consortium	EDM
Kitui	Complete	2022	UK	PACT	IIED , Loughborough University, <i>Caritas Kitui</i>	EDM
Laikipia	Ongoing		EU	SETA	SETA consortium	EDM
Makueni	Ongoing		EU	SETA	SETA consortium , Strathmore	EDM
Marsabit	Complete	2015	GIZ	N/A	Sawa Consulting , EED	Unknown
Meru	Ongoing		EU	SETA	SETA consortium	EDM
Migori	Ongoing		UK	PACT	Ricardo , KCCWG	Ricardo/KCCWG approach
Nairobi City	Complete	2016	UK	Starck+	Unknown , KAM, EED	Unknown
Nakuru	Complete	2022	GIZ, EU	CoM SSA	EED	EED approach
Narok	Complete	2022	UK	PACT	Strathmore , WRI, KEFRI, KCCWG, <i>NCNRN</i>	Strathmore approach
Nyandarua	Ongoing		EU	SETA	SETA consortium	EDM
Taita Taveta	Ongoing		EU	SETA	SETA consortium	EDM
Tana River	Ongoing		UK	PACT	Ricardo , KCCWG	Ricardo/KCCWG approach
Turkana	Complete	2016	GIZ	N/A	EED	EED approach
Vihiga	Ongoing		EU	SETA	SETA consortium	EDM

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

ACTS	African Centre for Technology Studies
CEC	County Executive Committee
CEP	County Energy Plan
CIDP	County Integrated Development Plan
CSO	Civil Society Organisation
CoM SSA	Covenant of Mayors in Sub-Saharan Africa
EDM	Energy Delivery Model
GDC	Geothermal Development Company
GIZ	Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit
IED	Innovation Energie Développement
IIED	International Institute for Environment and Development
INEP	Integrated National Energy Plan
KCCWG	Kenya Climate Change Working Group
KEFRI	Kenya Forestry Research Institute
KenGen	Kenya Electricity Generation Company
KETRACO	Kenya Electricity Transmission Company
LEAP	Low Emissions Analysis Platform
MoE	Ministry of Energy
NuPEA	Nuclear Power and Energy Agency
OnSSET	Open-Source Spatial Electrification Tool
REREC	Rural Electrification and Renewable Energy Corporation
SEAF-K	Sustainable Energy Access Forum - Kenya
SETA	Sustainable Energy Technical Assistance
UK PACT	UK Partnering for Accelerated Climate Transitions
WRI	World Resources Institute

1. Introduction

This working paper maps the ecosystem of actors involved in county-level energy planning in Kenya. Counties in Kenya are mandated by the 2019 Energy Act¹ to produce County Energy Plans (CEPs) every three years, which are intended to inform national energy planning and policy at the Ministry of Energy (MoE). A complex web of funders, organizations, and governmental bodies currently collaborate to produce these plans, using different approaches and operating on different timescales. The complexity of this space makes it difficult to enter or work within unless already entrenched within it.

This working paper seeks to map this complex ecosystem. Information was sourced via engagements (i.e., workshops and interviews) with organizations supporting county-level energy planning in Kenya at present. It is hoped that this can serve as a concise summary of ongoing work in this space, and as a quick start guide to anyone seeking to engage within it.

1.1 Policy Background

The Constitution of Kenya (2010) devolved political and administrative authority to Kenya's 47 counties with the aim to address developmental imbalances perpetuated by centralized governance systems². One of the functions devolved to county governments in Schedule Four of the Constitution is planning and development of energy, electricity, and gas.

Following the introduction of the 2019 Energy Act, county-level energy planning efforts in Kenya have accelerated. Of note is the European Union-funded Sustainable Energy Technical Assistance programme (SETA), which has provided baseline energy planning training to 46 counties and is now conducting advanced training leading to CEP development with 12 counties using the Energy Delivery Models (EDM) framework. However, there are other independent county energy planning efforts undertaken with separate funding and implementing organizations.

1.2 Contribution

This working paper investigates the ecosystem of actors involved in county energy planning in Kenya to answer the following questions:

- Who is involved in county-level energy planning in Kenya?
- How do they interrelate in terms of communication, power dynamics, and roles?
- Who is missing from this space?

By doing so, it aims to identify where there may be communication issues or inconsistencies which hamper sustainable and smooth county level energy planning in Kenya. As county-level energy planning efforts increase, clear communication lines institutional structures must be established to support them and make them sustainable.

2. Method

This working paper draws on information from workshops and stakeholder interviews. An **online workshop** was undertaken in July 2022 on the general topic of county energy planning in Kenya. Eight professional practitioners representing eight organizations or programmes supporting county energy planning efforts in Kenya attended the workshop. The discussion from this workshop was recorded and transcribed to capture insights. Discussion prompts covered several topics - the full list of discussion prompts is included in Appendix A. Ecosystem-centered points were:

- Who are the main stakeholders engaged in your county energy planning process?
- How do they interconnect?
- Where is the conversation not going well?
- Who else is missing from this process?

Following the workshop, individual **semi-structured interviews** were arranged. In total, 23 professionals representing 15 different organizations or programmes supporting county energy planning were interviewed. Three of the interviewees also attended the workshop – these follow-up interviews were scheduled to enable them to elaborate on their views in more detail. The remaining interviewees were not able to attend the workshop – these interviews were arranged to capture the insights and experiences of as many organizations involved in county energy planning as possible, identified through snowball sampling. Interview questions covered multiple dimensions of county energy planning. The full list of discussion prompts is included in Appendix B. The ecosystem-related prompts were the following:

- Which counties is your organization currently working with for county energy planning? What role does your organization play in supporting these counties?
- What other actors are involved in the planning work you are undertaking? What roles do the other actors play?
- Which stakeholders in county-level governance have you found to be particularly engaged?
- Does your organization partner with any civil society organizations for county energy planning? If so, what role do these organizations play?
- Who is funding your organization's work in county energy planning?
- Have there been any communication challenges with different stakeholders? Have you found any stakeholders to be very open and communicative?
- Are there any stakeholders which you feel are missing from the conversation?

Interviews were recorded and transcribed to capture insights. There was some overlap between interviewees and workshop participants. In total, 28 professionals representing 19 organizations or programmes supporting county energy planning were represented. Interviewees were assigned numeric codes to preserve anonymity.

Quotes are used below to illustrate key findings. They have all identifying information removed and are labelled with the interviewee code number, appended with “-I” to indicate that the quote was from an interview or “-W” to indicate that the quote was from the workshop.

Note that throughout the results, organisation webpages are hyperlinked for more information.

3. Results and Discussion

As expected, counties at Kenya are at different stages of county energy planning and supported by different partners. The status of those counties with ongoing or complete CEP work are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Kenyan counties with ongoing or complete county energy plans, as well as their funders, programmes, implementing organizations, and the approach undertaken.

County	CEP Status	Year	Funder	Programme	Organizations (lead in bold , local partner in <i>italics</i>)	Approach
Baringo	Ongoing		UK	PACT	Ricardo , KCCWG	Ricardo/KCCWG approach
Bomet	Ongoing		EU	SETA	SETA consortium , KCCWG, SEAF-K	EDM
Garissa	Ongoing		EU	SETA	SETA consortium	EDM
Kakamega	Ongoing		EU	SETA	SETA consortium	EDM
Kiambu	Ongoing		EU	SETA	SETA consortium	EDM
Kilifi	Ongoing		EU	SETA	SETA consortium	EDM
Kisii	Ongoing		EU	SETA	SETA consortium	EDM
Kitui	Complete	2022	UK	PACT	IIED , Loughborough University, <i>Caritas Kitui</i>	EDM
Laikipia	Ongoing		EU	SETA	SETA consortium	EDM
Makueni	Ongoing		EU	SETA	SETA consortium , Strathmore	EDM
Marsabit	Complete	2015	GIZ	N/A	Sawa Consulting , EED	Unknown
Meru	Ongoing		EU	SETA	SETA consortium	EDM
Migori	Ongoing		UK	PACT	Ricardo , KCCWG	Ricardo/KCCWG approach
Nairobi City	Complete	2016	UK	Starck+	Unknown , KAM, EED	Unknown
Nakuru	Complete ³	2022	GIZ, EU	CoM SSA	EED	EED approach
Narok	Complete	2022	UK	PACT	Strathmore , WRI, KEFRI, KCCWG, <i>NCNRN</i>	Strathmore approach
Nyandarua	Ongoing		EU	SETA	SETA consortium	EDM
Taita Taveta	Ongoing		EU	SETA	SETA consortium	EDM
Tana River	Ongoing		UK	PACT	Ricardo , KCCWG	Ricardo/KCCWG approach
Turkana	Complete	2016	GIZ	N/A	EED	EED approach
Vihiga	Ongoing		EU	SETA	SETA consortium	EDM

Status of energy planning across counties

Six counties have a complete CEP: Kitui, Marsabit, Nairobi, Nakuru, Narok, and Turkana. Fifteen counties have ongoing efforts to produce CEPs. The remaining 26 counties have made no official progress towards producing a CEP. Note that Nairobi's CEP was scrapped due to poor quality.

Funders

The United Kingdom (UK), Germany, and the European Union (EU) are the major funders of CEP development.

UK: The [Starck+](#) programme funded the production of the Nairobi CEP. The UK Partnering for Accelerated Climate Transitions ([UK PACT](#)) programme funded the production of the Kitui and Narok CEP⁴. It also supports CEP development in Baringo, Migori, and Tana River.

EU: The EU funds the [SETA](#) programme which is now supporting development of CEPs in twelve counties (i.e., Bomet, Garissa, Kakamega, Kiambu, Kilifi, Kisii, Laikipia, Makueni, Meru, Nyandarua, Taita Taveta, Vihiga). The EU also partially funded the CEP for Nakuru under Covenant of Mayors in Sub-Saharan Africa ([CoM SSA](#)).

Germany: GIZ has funded CEP development in Marsabit, Nakuru, and Turkana. They have been reported to have a good reputation in development spaces in Kenya, including in energy.

“You come under the banner of GIZ, the response you get is quite, is quite good, because people want to engage, because they know GIZ helps us in agriculture, GIZ helps us elsewhere, so they want to take this seriously, you know, so they would sit up straight and listen to you and give you the document and be responsive.” [13-1]

Organizations

CEP development is supported by both private sector organizations and Civil Society Organisations (CSOs). The SETA programme is implemented by a consortium including Innovation Energie Développement ([IED](#)), [Loughborough University](#), the African Centre for Technology Studies ([ACTS](#)), [Practical Action](#), and the International Institute for Environment and Development ([IIED](#)). They sometimes also draw in different organizations to support their work in specific ways (e.g., Strathmore University in Makueni), and are embedded in the MoE.

“SETA is run by a consortium of consultants. So it means we are under the Ministry of Energy, and of course the, the, the resource - there is a part of the resource are provided by IED, part of resource are provided by PACT, and part of the resource are providing, provided by LU and IIED, and other consultants so. But in fact is not PACT interacting with ministry or IED interacting with the ministry, but the consortium of consultant with, with one single contract with EU interacting with the ministry. And not interacting, because we are part of the ministry.” [12-1]

Kenya Climate Change Working Group ([KCCWG](#)) and Sustainable Energy Access Forum Kenya ([SEAF-K](#)), two members of the [Access Coalition](#), are also involved in supporting CEP production. KCCWG was sub-contracted by [Ricardo](#) to deliver three CEPs under UK PACT. In Narok, [Strathmore University](#), the World Resources Institute ([WRI](#)), and the Kenya Forestry Research Institute ([KEFRI](#)) collaborated to deliver the CEP. [EED Advisory](#), a private consulting firm, delivered the Turkana and Nakuru CEPs and assisted on several other CEPs.

Local Partners

CEP development is often supported by local partners. For instance, in Kitui, [Caritas Kitui](#) was engaged. CEP development in Narok also engaged the [Narok County National Resource Network](#). The 12 counties being supported by SETA at present are also partnering with local CSOs for data collection. In general, it is reported that these organizations bring excellent on-the-ground expertise which makes it easier to hit the ground running in different contexts.

“[The CSO] is grassroots-based, so that they bring out rich knowledge on community mobilization and understanding the dynamics ... the same reasoning has been applied to the SETA project in that, in the 11 mirroring counties, they have actually co-opted civil society organizations that are based in those counties who have been working closely with the communities so they understand the community structure, the way they are organized.” [3-W]

“So working with CSO – basically, the majority of them, they’re quite capable and they have been engaged at grassroots level, so they understand the ground level.” [17-I]

“The government in [county], they weren't very effective ... basically [CSO] was the main driver of it all basically, they're really good and obviously they know they knew the county context really well.” [6-I]

It was reported to be important that the CSOs are well-liked by county governance. If the relationship is good, things can proceed smoothly; if not, things may be more difficult. For this reason, the SETA programme largely leaves the choice of CSO to the county government.

“We largely left it to the counties to appoint the CSO that they wanted to work with. Because we felt that they have a better view of which CSO is involved in energy, or which CSO they are able to work with, because we didn't want to impose a CSO on a county government, because you know sometimes, it's often a bit of - you know, the relationship between county government and the civil society will vary from one place to another, and depending on the, the, the CSO - so we gave them that free hand, and somehow hoped that they will be able to appoint a suitable CSO.” [11-I]

National Governance and Parastatals

Key partners reported at the national level are as follows:

Kenya Power: [Kenya Power](#) (also referred to as KPLC) is the most influential of the power sector parastatals in terms of energy system planning. They hold most of the data that is needed at county level to complete energy planning. Additionally, they cooperate with the MoE to create and fulfil national level planning exercises. Indeed, they produce an annual energy report⁵ which includes activities across multiple agencies including Kenya Electricity Generating Company ([KenGen](#)), Kenya Electricity Transmission Company ([KETRACO](#)), the Geothermal Development Corporation ([GDC](#)), and

the Nuclear Power and Energy Agency ([NuPEA](#)), showing their coordinating power in the sector. It is important to be cognizant in county energy planning discussions that Kenya Power is under a lot of pressure financially and socially to achieve its mandates, and this may influence its engagement. In addition, as a public limited company, Kenya Power bears the legal liability of customer data falling into the wrong hands; therefore, the proper channels should be followed in requesting data. Kenya Power is more comfortable availing the data to the MoE than the counties. For more information on this, please refer to the parallel working paper on data flows⁶.

“There's this big disconnect in Kenya, right, between the national planning and obviously, which also manifests itself in terms of KPLC getting into big debt, you know, and a lot of customer dissatisfaction.” [6-1]

Kenya National Bureau of Statistics: The bureau of statistics ([KNBS](#)) holds significant quantities of demographic and socioeconomic data which can be useful in energy planning. For instance, they conducted the 2019 census, the most comprehensive country-wide demographic survey⁷. However, they do not currently make this data available at the spatial resolution required by planners – it is available at sub-county level when ward-level is reportedly needed⁵. It was reported that from now on, KNBS will conduct quarterly (i.e., four times a year) household surveys, including energy data collection. The surveys will allow KNBS to collect data for county energy planning, if they can be officially notified about the required data.

“Going forward we will have quarterly Kenya continuous household survey program. We have managed to convince our DG to add an energy module to the program so we can monitor on quarterly basis the use of electricity and other energy fuels.” [25-1]

Ministry of Energy: The Ministry of Energy ([MoE](#)) is creating the Integrated National Energy Planning (INEP) framework, which is intended to guide the production of both national energy plans and CEPs going forward. MoE is responsible for high-level national energy planning to date (e.g., the Kenya National Electrification Strategy of 2018⁸). They are intended to aggregate the CEPs into a useful output for national-level plans and agencies to use. Their go-ahead has been found to be needed by other organisation at times to release critical data to support county energy planning. The ministry is committed to creating a centralised energy database to have all energy data in one place – they are seeking partnerships to actualise this.

“We want the database to be a kind of reporting with automatic updates. The reporting is already being done, but through email exchange. We want it in such a way that we can easily access different energy related information at different administrative levels. This will give us the flexibility to do the modelling ... We want someone who can help us to make the energy dashboard fast.” [26-1]

“We are working directly with the Ministry of Energy, who are like the project owners of the SETA project, so to ensure that what we are, what, what we are developing with the counties reflect, of course, the INEP framework that was developed by the ministry. ... So essentially everything that we are doing is working collaboratively with the with the Ministry of Energy ... I think on our part we are working closely with KPLC and also REREC.” [3-W]

“We worked, of course, with the national government agencies, so REREC ... ERPA, and you know KPLC and the others.” [13-I]

Rural Electrification and Renewable Energy Corporation: [REREC](#) handles the planning for some rural electrification, especially off-grid projects involving mini-grids. It is important for those producing CEPs to be informed about their plans to ensure that they are in alignment. REREC can also partner with counties to implement electrification projects through their matching fund program. Through the program, REREC matches the budget amount counties commit to electrification projects to a maximum of KES 5 million per constituency.

“We [REREC] have a "Matching Fund" program. We tell the counties give us this much [money] then we will match that will a similar amount depending on the number of constituencies in the county. We cap the matching to KES 5 million per constituency. Then the counties get to identify their priority areas for electrification" [21-I]

County Governance

Key partners at county level are as follows:

County Executive Committee (CEC): The CEC consists of ministers responsible for many of the functions of county governance, individually referred to as CECs. While one CEC has responsibility for energy, they also tend to have several other portfolios (e.g., climate, environment). These ministers may not have the technical knowledge to undertake energy planning if their expertise falls under one of the other portfolios. Additionally, they are frequently under-resourced and over-stretched. Finally, different ministries at county level are reported to work in a very siloed way.

“Most of the county don't have a dedicated CEC for energy, it's always energy, environment, water or energy public works and something. ... The counties are just being bombarded by all these people trying to help them, right, in different ways, telling them they need to come up with a climate change policy, you need to come up with this and you need to come up with that. So then, and then, in addition to that they have their day job, which is ensuring that you know public works, environment and all these things are done in the county, because that's why they're there primarily. So it can be quite overwhelming.” [13-I]

“They don't have an energy expert or they, they don't have somebody who's designated to lead energy work, because then the energy programme or the energy docket is actually together with the environment, it - quite a number of other dockets put together, and the person who's leading this piece of work probably doesn't have expertise in the energy field. They probably have expertise, yes, in the environment field, but then they don't have expertise in the energy field.” [1-W]

“The other thing is to try to make it cross-sectorial because planning is a very, you know, even though in CIDPs it's supposed to be an integrated planning process and that's the director of plan-planning supposed to put together, in reality different ministries do their planning a very siloed way” [6-I]

County Assemblies: The county assembly is one of the main governing organs in the County structure. It was reported that overall, these assemblies may not at present prioritize energy. As such, it is important to communicate the benefits of energy such that it is prioritized.

“it's very important then to bring on board the political aspect of policy making in terms of the county assemblies, you know, they just to really make them understand this need for energy planning and for them to be able to prioritise it, because as it is now, it's really not ingrained in some of the county assemblies to see this as a very important aspect of development in the counties.” [8-W]

Directors: The Director for Economic Planning is responsible for creating the County Integrated Development Plan (CIDP). This makes them a key focal point in aggregating planning efforts across different county departments. As they sit slightly higher than the different departments in terms of sway and power, they hold more authority to make demands of data across departments, coordinate efforts, and so on. The Director for Energy is also a key contact point.

“if you go to the CEC energy because you're doing energy stuff, right, but the energy stuff cannot be done without talking to people in agriculture, people in water, the people in education. So when the, then there's someone else talking to people in agriculture. So I think this should be taken one notch higher, so even when we go to the county and say, look, we want to work with you on your county energy plan, we should not be directed to the CEC, we should be directed to the officers in charge of the CIDP ... so that there is kind of one-stop coordination on planning, all planning aspects needs to be coordinated. And then from there then it can cascade downwards to the CEC.” [13-I]

“At a county level, we try to work together with Director of Energy and the Director of Economic Planning because it will link directly with the preparation of CIDP.” [12-I]

“To ensure that those plans are clearly moved just from plans to being implemented ... the best way is to ensure that they find their way into the County Integrated Development Plans running from next year to 2027 ... take the director for planning to be our focal person in the entire county energy planning process ... the director has ensured, has actually ensured, I mean - uh, yes ensure that what, what we are planning will find its way into the County Integrated Development Plan.” [3-W]

“I wouldn't want to look at energy as a stand-alone, but actually much more about energy as an enabler of development, and I think every county wants, basically to inspire economic or social development in their counties. And the only place where you hear people articulate all these development priorities? Well, it's in the County Integrated Development Plan.” [2-W]

The County Governor: The County Governor holds perhaps the most sway of any official at county level. It is important to establish a good relationship with the governor to facilitate CEP work, as they can play a key role in ensuring different CECs and departments prioritize the work. They are also important members for engagement from national level – in the past, where they have not been consulted, this has caused problems.

“Why should I listen to the Department of Energy? They're my peers right? But if it comes from the office of the governor there, there's, there's better coordination, there's better response” [13-1]

“There was a pushback as far as understand from the Council of Governors about the lack of consultation on INEP.” [6-i]

Engaging with County Governance

It has been reported that, to foster good relationships with county governments and genuine engagement, it is important to work with them prior to any start of work on county energy planning. Garnering buy-in with these officials was highlighted to be of equal importance to producing the plan itself. In addition, it is noted to be effective to have a designated contact person at the county level who can mobilise others as needed.

“We started engaging the county even before the official project in order to understand their needs and, and also how to get their buy-in. After that, we started to understand in terms of data the data which they have ... Apart from supporting them [to] develop the county energy plan, we are also building the capacity so that when we leave they are able to review and they will update the data plan themselves.” [7-W]

“Getting county government officials even participating in your meetings virtually - for me it's not something that I would take for granted.” [1-W]

“You must ensure that there is buy in for the process from the start. Some members might say that they didn’t take part in the process, so they don’t want to be associated with the document ... You have to agree with them [officials] on the methodology, including the sample size and how this sample will be collected” [24-I]

“You need someone who carries the burden of coordinating – a mobiliser who can go to people physically if emails don’t work to iron out on the best time to hold workshops or to give feedback on work done” [23-I]

“It’s also important to remember that it’s not just about the energy plan, it’s about the, the buy-in that’s created as you as you try to do it. So, so to not just be purely extractive, but to be kind of building the, the understanding and consensus as you go, otherwise it will just remain a kind of a long document on the shelf.” [2-W]

“This sort of structure started all the way, perhaps even before the project. So, there was for example the, the formation of the steering committee - that was by the senior, senior level of the county government. To us, it was a little bracing, because the county governor, uh, you know, inaugurated the formation of the steering committee.” [5-W]

Additionally, many capacity gaps are reported in county governance. This can prevent CECs and department staff from engaging with the CEP process at depth, even if they are enthusiastic to do so. This highlights the importance of capacity building efforts as part of CEP.

“The training is mostly we are targeting the government officials, because that is where we find the biggest gaps.” [11-I]

“I remember, for one county, we will send them documents, and they will not give us comments, and then we were getting a bit frustrated. But then we realized that they may not necessarily know or have the capability of reviewing a document, and for example saying we want growth rates of 10% versus 12% or 15%. Like, when we are, when we are doing goal setting sessions, we find it difficult – like, on what basis should we say universal access by 2027 versus 2030 right?” [13-I]

Planning Approaches Across Actors

The most common approach undertaken in CEP production is the Energy Delivery Model (EDM). EDM is a three-phase pro-poor approach which was developed by IIED⁹. It has been tested in Indonesia¹⁰ and was used to produce the CEP for Kitui County¹¹. Training material has been developed for EDM¹², which has been tested in several recent projects. All counties supported by the SETA programme are intended to produce CEPs using the EDM approach.

SETA begins their process with a basic training programme. This has been delivered to 44 of Kenya’s 47 counties and provides general guidance on energy planning. Of those who completed this basic

training, 12 were selected to carry onto an advanced training programme, which now supports the production of their CEPs.

“We give them some information about the political background in energy, political backgrounds and select development of strategy - for example, gender, energy efficiency, bioenergy, and so on - and then going to say, OK, now this program is to train you, and part of you will continue with the more detailed approach.” [12-I]

It is important to note that it has been reported that, due to budgetary cuts, some aspects of needs assessment in the EDM process have been cut in the 11 other counties mirroring Meru.

“There's been a sort of unilateral decision ... to kind of modify the EDM process ... and only do certain elements. So to be honest with you, the needs, the actual going to communities and doing needs assessment workshops has been cut considerably ... I think there's a lack of understanding of the methodology, and understanding of that real need to look at energy as an enabler.” [6-I]

While the EDM process incorporates thorough capacity building and nuanced consideration of energy as an enabler across developmental siloes, it is also quite resource intensive in the short term and it is unclear whether all the nuanced data collected therein is used. This was raised by several stakeholders as a concern, as it may lead to cynicism about the planning exercise if an extensive effort is made to plan but the plan and data collected do not end up being used.

“I've raised the concern with the EDM because - it's, it's very complicated, right? It requires a lot of effort, but that's not the problem. The problem is, what do you do with all that detail, right? Because already even some counties ... they are asking themselves, like, what do we get by engaging in the CEP? ... How did that change our lives, right? So the, the, what SETA is using is really good. I think it's very detailed, but we have to ask ourselves, can they sustain that? Can the county governments sustain that, plus, are we using all that information? Yeah, so we're collecting all these solutions, but are we using it? ... There's an element of raising expectations with the people that you are talking to, because you ask them, what do you want? ... I do have reservations with the EDM, but not, not with the process itself, but it being the approach for the CEP. And SETA does know that.” [13-I]

“The positives [of EDM] are ... if you get the kind of buy-in, it does build a kind of ongoing capacity for like planning and problem solving in the people that participate in it, I think it ... builds understanding amongst decision makers about energy as an enabler, and the relevance of energy to other sectors and not just this kind of siloed thing. And I think it does really bring in the needs of communities, and citizens that kind of needs-based process. And they’re kind of coming up with actually really costed solutions ... that idea that really trying to come up with holistic, not, you know, not just energy, but non-energy solutions, and you're, but you're really costing that, and you're really looking at the viability of it ... it's not just based on some kind of wishful thinking thing. So, there's that getting much more concrete and real about planning, I think. And the negatives, obviously, I mean, it's very dependent on the level of buy-in of the government and the, the sort of political economy of each county. ... I think it is resource intensive, in the sense of human resource intensive and commitment intensive. I mean, obviously, we argue that like if you look at it sort of like the cost of failed investments, investing in the actual planning process is, you know, is a kind of - actually saves you money in the long term, but obviously, you know, if, where people are used to, you know, with the CIDPs, bringing in a consultant or, you know, that's the approach, you just bring in someone or you just do a, a paper job, you don't do a lot of needs assessment, you don't invest in - so we, you know, you do get a bit of that, well, why do you need to kind of know this? And what, why do we need to kind of do this?” [6-I]

However, other approaches have been developed. These include the approaches developed by Strathmore, Ricardo/KCCWG and EED to produce CEPs in the counties they support. While none of these approaches are as well documented as EDM, that does not necessarily make them less effective. As CEPs supported by Strathmore and Ricardo/KCCWG are forthcoming, it will be interesting in future work to compare these different approaches.

While each approach has its own details, several borrow from the EDM principle. As the only approach to county energy planning with public-facing documentation and training material provided, this is unsurprising.

“We borrowed quite much on the EDM principle, or the methodology has already shared by [name]. It, we found it to be a very, a very good principle.” [7-W]

“There's a lot of interlinkages and cross-borrowing I think from the EDM model.” [8-W]

In some cases, where CEPs have been produced by one-off consultants, the approach is minimally documented. In speaking with actors presently involved in the ecosystem, it was impossible to ascertain how CEPs developed by one-off consultants (i.e., in Nairobi or Marsabit) were completed. This is the issue that presents when these approaches are poorly documented.

Comparing approaches is difficult when documentation and resulting CEPs are not public facing. Of all CEPs presently produced, the research team has only been able to find one published online

(i.e., Nakuru’s plan produced by EED). Furthermore, while the EDM approach is well-documented in theory and now being widely applied, no example of a plan produced with this approach is available publicly online. Even if these plans are available internally in the energy sector, a lack of public visibility makes it difficult to transparently assess the process.

All approaches attempt in some way to follow the INEP framework. Views are mixed on the INEP as it stands, but generally speaking, practitioners seem to indicate that it is a good starting point. INEP is still undergoing review prior to its official launch via cabinet secretary circular – it is hoped that some of these issues will be addressed before it is put formally into law.

“The ministry have developed a template, I’m sure you’ve seen the template - it’s very long, it’s 75 pages and we gave feedback that it’s just too long. We, we thought it’s, it, it doesn’t work, and also it’s too prescriptive... I think there just needs to be a bare minimum requirement, and then the county themselves need to kind of fill in what is a priority for them ... My views have always been like, keep the outline very basic, keep it very basic and very targeted at being points of outputs to the INEP, so it’s not just this 150 page document, just leafing around, right? So, the outline from the national government should be very specific, and then the county need to, just inspire, over and above that, so if they want to do 200 pages, you know, all the best.” [13-I]

“When you look at the INEP framework, it’s very general, really. I mean, they have this for the CEP, they have this kind of very general process, and then they have basically, you know, the chapters of the CEP, what the content supposed to be and to be able to, in terms of data, some of it is a bit nonsensical. It’s a bit like well, what do they actually need this data for? How is this really going to help with planning?” [6-I]

“I think INEP is great in, in that it’s a kind of policy acknowledgement that there’s a need for more integrated planning and particularly between the kind of national and the subnational levels. I think it, you know, in terms of methodologies to actually operationalize INEP, I think that’s still a gap. It gives the kind of chapter outlines for the CEP, but for most counties, it just basically says you know this is the content of the chapter, it doesn’t actually tell, you know, support counties to do it.” [6-W]

4. Reflections and Moving Forward

The county energy planning space in Kenya is undoubtedly complex. For the research team to gain an appreciation of the scope of actors, their roles and engagements, and the dynamics between them, it required several weeks and many conversations, despite our relative familiarity with the Kenyan energy sector. It seems that with every new conversation, new nuggets of information emerged. We cannot be certain that the entire state of play has even been captured in this work.

As such, we can confidently conclude that a coordinating mechanism in the county energy planning space is needed. It has been suggested that SETA plays this role, and indeed, they unite many of the actors at present. However, it is important to note that SETA is a time-limited EU-funded programme. For county level energy planning to become sustainably implemented at county level, and for the sector to avoid dysfunction, conflict, and duplication of effort, we recommend some coordination of this web of actors to be institutionally embedded in governance structures. In the meantime, we hope that this report can serve as a useful reference point.

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Appendix A: Workshop Discussion Prompts

- Overview of the county-level planning approaches used in the group
- Benefits and disadvantages of the approaches used (including cross-county comparisons)
- How well do the approaches complement each other?
- Data discussion: What data is used in participant's county level planning approach? How is it managed? Is the data open? Why or why not? What data are missing to facilitate the different approaches?
- Who are the main stakeholders engaged in your county energy planning process?
- How do they interconnect?
- Where is the conversation not going well?
- Who else is missing from this process?

Appendix B: Interview Discussion Prompts

Approach:

- Which counties is your organization is currently working with for county energy planning?
- What role does your organization play in supporting county energy planning in these counties?
- How would you describe your organization's approach in supporting county energy planning?
- Is there a particular method you follow or align with?
- How does this differ from approaches used by other organizations?
- Do you use models or tools to enable county-level energy planning?
- Is your approach documented anywhere?
- Are there other counties that your organization planning to work with in the future?

Stakeholders:

- Aside from your organization, what other actors are involved in the planning work you are undertaking, and what roles do they play?
- Which stakeholders in county-level governance have you found to be particularly important or engaged in this work?
- Does your organization partner with any civil society organizations for county energy planning? If so, what role do these organizations play?
- Who is funding your organization's work in county energy planning?
- How does the your organization approach incorporate community engagement?
- When working with these different organizations and stakeholders, have there been any communication challenges?
- Have there been any stakeholders which you've found to be very open and communicative?
- Are there any stakeholders or actors which have been difficult to contact, or which you feel are missing from the county energy planning conversation?

Data:

- What data is critical to your organization planning efforts?
- Is the data you need available? Are there any challenges in working with available data?
- What data gaps has your organization faced in county energy planning work?
- Has your organization need to collect any data to facilitate planning efforts? If so, what have you collected?
- Is the data your organization collects shared with other organizations, or made open source? Why or why not?

Policy & Politics:

- Has your organization found that the Integrated National Energy Planning (INEP) framework provides adequate guidance for how county energy planning should be completed? Why or why not?
- What challenges, if any, has your organization faced working with county governance on energy planning?
- Has your organization worked with any national agencies or organizations? If so, could you talk about the working relationship with them? How could national agencies better support county energy planning, in your experience?
- Are there any political challenges that your organization has faced in these county energy planning efforts, either at the county or national level?

Collaboration:

- How does your organization interact with other organizations working in county energy planning?
- Would you find a regular forum across different organizations supporting county energy planning to be useful? Why or why not?